

Role of soluble organic matters, particularly orthodihydroxy phenolic types of compounds in natural waters as potential inhibitors for the manifestation of uranyl (UO_2^{2+}) fluorescence : a preliminary communication

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Abstract : A significant finding on the role of soluble organic matters, particularly orthodihydroxy phenols and naphthols in the suppression/inhibition of uranium fluorescence in water samples is reported.

Most natural water samples do contain a number of soluble organic compounds having capacity to form chelates/complexes with metal ions present in these waters. The organic load in natural water varies with the degree of pollution/eutrication of water bodies. Some of the soluble organic ligands such as phenolic compounds, amino acids, fulvic acids, etc. form so strong complexes with UO_2^{2+} ion that it cannot come out of the clutch of such complexes in order to form phosphate complex with fluorescence enhancing buffer such as fluran or pyrophosphoric acid used to measure uranium fluorescence.

This phenomenon has been thoroughly verified/demonstrated in our laboratory by using a host of organic compounds, mostly phenols and naphthols which are expected to be present in natural water samples. Heavy suppression of uranium fluorescence has been observed with a number of such compounds. In line with this, suppression of uranium fluorescence in real water samples have also been observed.

After destruction of the soluble organic compounds present in water samples, the actual fluorescence of uranium present in these waters could be successfully measured. Measurement of uranium fluorescence in most water samples is faulty unless a prior destruction of these soluble organic compounds is resorted to.

Keywords : Fluorescence measurement, uranium, orthodihydroxy organic compounds, fluorescence enhancing buffer.

Introduction

Uranium(VI) [UO_2^{2+}] in significant concentrations may be transported through a wide range of Eh and pH conditions as various uranyl complexes^{1,2}. The transport and deposition of uranium in natural waters is controlled by the organic and inorganic chemistry of the water involved.

As already established, organic species present in most natural waters fluoresce quite intensely but their emission does not last longer than the relatively long persistence of the uranyl fluorescence by the addition of fluorescence enhancing reagent. Electronic 'gating' is employed in the instrument, Scintrex UA-3 Uranium Analyzer developed by J. C. Robbins³, to separate the long lived contribution, rejecting substantially the organic fluorescence.

However, in his very paper, he had also mentioned, although not in clear-cut term that soluble organic mat-

ters like humic acid which he used in the interference test, severely reduced the uranyl fluorescence at 10 ppm level, and suggested for further investigations.

It was also mentioned that the response of the instrument after addition of FLURAN to a uranium bearing solution is usually very rapid, except in the case of some organic rich samples, when the extraction of uranium from the organic species appears to be rather slow.

Organic rich waters may present another set of problems in interpretation⁴. Formation of soluble heavy metal organic complexes has been demonstrated⁵, but the extent to which this occurs in natural waters will be controlled by competition for complexing sites between trace metals and major cations.

Uranium is also known to be strongly adsorbed by solid organic materials, e.g. peat⁶ and inorganic materi-

als such as iron hydroxide and clays⁷ offering a variety of scavenging and precipitation mechanisms.

In view of the above, it appears that soluble organic and inorganic complexes of uranium(VI) have got an inhibiting effect on the manifestation of uranium fluorescence.

However, this aspect, in contrast to the natural fluorescence due to organic matters in natural waters has so far received least attention, and to our great surprise no report has so far been available in the literature probing the inhibiting effect of soluble organic compounds, many of which are potential complexing/chelating agents for uranyl ion having strong clutch over the bound/sequestered UO_2^{2+} , thereby not allowing it to be released during the addition of FLURAN/any fluorescence enhancing buffer while measuring fluorescence of uranium by laser fluorimetry.

Water samples, particularly those which are more or less stagnant contain appreciable amount of soluble organic compounds, mostly decomposition products of humic substrates and other soluble or insoluble organic substances. A large number of such soluble organic compounds occur in natural waters⁸. These products are generally phenolic compounds and their derivatives such as resorcinol, pyrogallol, catechol, naphthols, guaiacol and host of other compounds having *ortho*, *meta* and *para* dihydroxy groups. Of these, the *ortho* dihydroxy compounds are having propensity to form complexes with metal ions present in water in the pH range 7–8. Soluble uranyl (UO_2^{2+}) ion is expected to remain in these water samples bound as complexes of the organic/inorganic products. Because of their high stability, uranium is often difficult to be released from the clutche of these strong complexes, not allowing it to subsequently form species with the added phosphatic buffers, responsible for enhancing uranyl fluorescence. In such waters, the uranium(VI) fluorescence which is expected to be enhanced by the use of these fluorescence enhancing buffers added for facilitating fluorescence measurements is often blocked/inhibited by the soluble organic matters indicating non availability/less availability of uranium in such waters although appreciable uranium may actually be present. This entails a great deal of difficulty in analyzing the actual content of uranium in water samples with the available tools. Sometimes, uranium of the order of 100 ppb

shows negligible response due to the presence of such organic compounds in those waters. Geologists searching for uranium in those water bodies get wrong/baffling results, and the very purpose of hydrogeochemical survey for uranium is defeated.

In our laboratory, we could amply demonstrate this aspect by actually carrying out experiments with a number of synthetic solutions of such compounds, and allowing these to form complexes with uranyl (UO_2^{2+}) ion, and then the fluorescence of uranium bound with these compounds were tried to be measured with the laser fluorimeter using suitable fluorescence enhancing buffers, including the proprietary agent 'Fluran'. In fact, although appreciable quantity of uranium is present in such artificial/synthetic solutions prepared for study, no uranium fluorescence could be detected. It is because of the fact that the sequestered uranyl (UO_2^{2+}) ion cannot be dislodged from the strong clutches of the organic complexes of the metal ion by the added fluorescence enhancing buffers (phosphatic ligand). Once these complexes are broken by destroying organic matters, the released uranium readily forms complexes with the phosphatic ligands, thereby displaying intense uranium fluorescence. In line with our studies carried out with the artificial solution of these organic compounds, this very phenomenon has been amply demonstrated with a few such natural water samples having appreciable organic load (high DOC content).

In these samples, uranium fluorescence was either found to be almost negligible or it was quite feeble. However, when the organic contents of these water samples were destroyed, and the released uranium was allowed to form species responsible for manifesting uranium fluorescence, drastic changes observed i.e. fluorescence intensity often increased manifold.

These prompted us to undertake a systematic study on a host of such natural water samples having varied amount of dissolved organic compounds, mostly phenolic ones. We have performed experiments with a number of natural water samples collected from different field areas, and successfully demonstrated the role of such dissolved phenolic compounds in the measurement of uranium fluorescence in these water samples. The present paper encompasses the results obtained from the studies on this aspect. The present study which is highly useful from the point of view of uranium exploration shall usher in a

paradigm shift in the concept of fluorescence measurement of uranium in water samples.

Experimental

Apparatus/Instruments used : Laser Fluorimeter model UA-3 Uranium Analyser (Scintrex, Canada make) was used for fluorescence measurements ($\lambda_{\text{excitation}}$ 337 nm).

pH Meter : ELICO (LI-120) pH meter was used for pH measurements.

Laboratory hot plate was used for sample treatments and Muffle furnace was used for standard uranium solution preparation

Reagents :

All the reagents used were of AR/GR grade.

Stock uranium(VI) solution, 1 mg L⁻¹ as U₃O₈ :

A 1.0 g of uranyl nitrate, hexahydrate was heated at 850 °C in a Muffle furnace to convert it into U₃O₈ and then 0.1 g of U₃O₈ was dissolved in 50 ml HNO₃ and the volume was made up to 100 ml. The working solution was prepared from this stock solution by appropriate dilution.

Fig. 1. Plot of decrease in fluorescence intensity of uranium vs concentration of added organic compounds for the determination of 50 ppb of U₃O₈ : (A) 3,4-Dihydroxybenzaldehyde, (B) 2,3-Dihydroxynaphthalene.

Preparation of buffer :

Pyrophosphate buffer : Prepared by dissolving 25 g sodium pyrophosphate in 400 ml distilled water contained in a 1000 ml beaker. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 7 by adding phosphoric acid dropwise and the final volume was adjusted to 500 ml.

Sodium dihydrogenphosphate buffer :

It was prepared by dissolving sodium dihydrogen orthophosphate and orthophosphoric acid in distilled water maintaining their concentration 2.17 and 1.0 mol L⁻¹ respectively.

Fluran :

A 142.5 g of Na₃PO₄·12H₂O and 8.20 g Na₄P₂O₇·10 H₂O were taken in a 1 litre beaker. Approximately 375 ml of triple distilled water and about 10 ml of orthophosphoric acid were added to it, and then heated gently to dissolve. After dissolution cooled it and diluted to 500 ml with triple distilled water and the pH was adjusted to 6.9 with H₃PO₄. Or else the proprietary reagent can be imported from M/s Scintrex, Canada. All the experiments wherever needed were carried out using the imported proprietary reagent, 'Fluran'.

A 0.01 mol L⁻¹ stock solution of each of the reagent, 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene, 3,4-dihydroxybenzoic acid, 3,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde, pyrogallol, guaiacol etc. were prepared. The working solutions were prepared from this stock solution by appropriate dilution.

Preparation of synthetic/artificial solution (aqueous) of phenolic organic compounds :

Two sets of aqueous solution of the organic compounds containing appropriate/required amount of the organic ligand chosen from millimole to micromole levels were prepared. The organic compounds which are not water soluble are initially dissolved in least amount of acetone or methanol, and then finally dissolved in water.

Procedure :

(1) Direct fluorescence measurements :

Taken a suitable aliquot (2 ml) of appropriate pH in a cuvette and to it was added 2 ml of appropriate fluorescence enhancing buffer and mixed well. Volume of the solution was adjusted to 6 ml with triple distilled water. Measured the fluorescence of the solution in the laser fluorimeter (Scintrex UA-3 Uranium Analyzer) previously calibrated/standardized against standard uranium solution.

(2) Fluorescence measurement after destroying organic matter :

An aliquot (10 ml) of the same sample was taken in a 100 ml glass beaker. The solution was dried on a steam bath. About 5 drops of HClO₄ were added and moistened

the bottom surface of the beaker with HClO_4 . Transferred the beaker on a hot plate and heated till the fume of HClO_4 ceased to appear, allowed the beaker to cool, added 1 or 2 drops of HNO_3 and about 5 ml of triple distilled water. Allowed to dissolve the residue by heating it gently on a steam bath (at $\sim 100^\circ\text{C}$). Cooled the content and transferred the solution into a 10 ml volumetric flask and diluted the volume to 10 ml with triple distilled water. Pipetted 2 ml of this solution into the cuvette. Added 2 ml of requisite fluorescence enhancing buffer, mixed well, adjusted the volume to ~ 6 ml with triple distilled water and then measured the fluorescence of the solution in the same instrument (UA-3 Uranium Analyser make : Scintrex, Canada).

Results and discussions

While comparing the results of uranium determination by Laser Induced Fluorimetry (LIF) with those obtained from conventional fluorimetry after pre-concentrating the analyte either by simple evaporation of water samples or by co-precipitating uranium with hydrated titanium oxide, $\text{Ti}(\text{OH})_4$, it was often found that, the values obtained by LIF were always less than those obtained by conventional fluorimetry⁹.

Similar observations were recorded by Singh *et al.*¹⁰ while comparing the results of uranium estimation by LIF with those obtained by Fission-track method.

While developing colorimetric¹¹ and fluorimetric¹² methods for uranium determination in rock samples using guaiacol (orthomethoxyanisole) and 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene, both phenolic compounds and while trying to extend the methods to LIF, even with standard aqueous solutions having appreciably high uranium contents (~ 100 ppb), no uranium fluorescence signal could be obtained. From the above study, it was construed that probably, phenolic compounds, particularly those having orthodihydroxy groups might be inhibiting manifestation of uranium fluorescence in LIF.

Cameron¹³ in his paper stated that the effectiveness of the LIF method for uranium estimation in organic rich terrain such as the southern Canadian shield has been puzzling. It is suggested that the good mobility of uranium in such terrain may be explained by the presence of stable soluble organic uranium "complexes" that allow the metal to pass through organic rich traps.

In view of the above, it was conjectured that in nature UO_2^{2+} ion is usually mobile in surface waters in the form of soluble organic complexes, wherever such organic compounds are present. If organic compounds are not present in water, UO_2^{2+} ion is generally transported as soluble inorganic complexes of various anion like, CO_3^{2-} , F^- , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- etc.

The stability constants of uranium complexes with those soluble phenolic compounds may be so high that uranium is not released from these strong complexes, and therefore cannot form the species (complex) with the fluorescence enhancing phosphatic buffer, responsible for enhancing uranyl fluorescence.

This prompted us to undertake systematic studies on the effect of a selected number of representative phenolic compounds on the manifestation of uranium fluorescence.

Separate solutions of these phenolic compounds (3,4-dihydroxybenzoic acid, 3,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde, pyrogallol, guaiacol, 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene) were prepared over a wide concentration range (millimole to micromole) and their effect on uranium fluorescence was studied in detail. The results obtained have been shown in Table 1. This table clearly shows that at very high concentration of these soluble phenolic compounds (at millimole level), the uranium fluorescence is completely obliterated. However, with decrease in the concentration of these soluble organic compounds, the fluorescence signals of uranium gradually increased. The suppression of fluorescence signal is always there in the presence of these organic compounds.

Table 1. Fluorescence signals of 10 ppb U_3O_8 in presence of different organic compounds

Organic compounds	Fluorescence signal at a conc. of 1 millimolar of organic compounds	Fluorescence signal at a conc. of 50 micromolar of organic compounds	Fluorescence signal at a conc. of 20 micromolar of organic compounds
3,4-Dihydroxy benzoic acid	00	18	19
3,4-Dihydroxy benzaldehyde	00	03	16
Pyrogallol	00	02	13
Guaiacol	00	14	17
2,3-Dihydroxynaphthalene	00	06	19

In order to verify that the presence of these soluble organic compounds is the sole reason for inhibiting uranium fluorescence, the organic compounds in these synthetic samples were destroyed by treating these with mixture of nitric and perchloric acids, and the fluorescence measurements were carried out. The results obtained are shown in Table 2 which clearly shows that with the destruction of the added organic compounds in uranium solution, the fluorescence intensity of each solution recouped to the full extent.

In some of the real samples, the extent of signal suppression is upto ~100%. This clearly shows that measurements of uranium fluorescence in untreated waters are often faulty, depending on the content of the soluble organic compounds.

From the above study, it is inferred that the extent of fluorescence inhibiting effect of different soluble compounds are different, depending upon the chelating ability of respective soluble compounds.

Table 2. Fluorescence signals of 10 ppb U_3O_8 in presence of different organic compounds and after destroying the organic compounds

Organic compounds	Fluorescence signal at a conc. of 1 millimolar of organic compounds		Fluorescence signal at a conc. of 50 micromolar of organic compounds		Fluorescence signal at a conc. of 20 micromolar of organic compounds	
	As such	After destroying organic matters	As such	After destroying organic matters	As such	After destroying organic matters
	3,4-Dihydroxy benzoic acid	00	22	18	22	19
3,4-Dihydroxy benzaldehyde	00	23	03	23	16	23
Pyrogallol	00	23	02	21	13	23
Guaicol	00	22	14	23	17	23
2,3-Dihydroxynaphthalene	00	23	06	23	19	23

Measurement of uranium fluorescence in a set of real water samples collected from field areas were carried out in the similar fashion as done with synthetic solutions.

The results obtained have been shown in the Tables 3 and 4. Different buffer systems [in-house as well as the imported proprietary one (Fluran)] have been used. In both the cases, the results obtained are found to be in line with those obtained with synthetic solutions.

This clearly shows that the soluble phenolic organic compounds have a definite suppressive/inhibiting effect on the fluorescence intensity of uranyl ion in water samples.

Table 4. Measurement of uranium fluorescence intensity in water sample (using pyrophosphate buffer) (n = 3)

Serial No.	Sample	Direct	After $HClO_4$ treatment
1.	L-105	08	15
2.	L-109	10	32
3.	L-125	09	14
4.	L-140	15	17
5.	L-151	06	12
6.	L-167	04	06
7.	L-174	10	12

Table 3. Measurement of uranium fluorescence intensity in water sample (using Fluran buffer) (n = 3)

Serial No.	Sample	Direct	After $HClO_4$ treatment
1.	L-19	50	68
2.	AMD-1	00	04
3.	L-78	12	14
4.	L-86	40	48
5.	L-105	20	28
6.	L-109	00	75

Conclusion

The study carried out in the laboratory has given a new insight in to the field of fluorescence measurement of uranium in natural water samples by LIF. Determination of uranium by LIF in untreated water samples having soluble organic compounds, which form soluble uranium complexes, often yields faulty results, misleading investigating geologists engaged in geochemical exploration for uranium.

Prior destruction of organic matter in all the water samples is a must for obtaining accurate results of ura-

nium determination by LIF. Further work correlating DOC (Dissolved Organic Carbon) of water samples with their suppressing effect on the fluorescence intensity of uranyl ion as well as measurements of uranium fluorescence in synthetic water samples containing a wide variety of soluble organic compounds generally expected to be present in natural water samples is in progress.

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